

ANALYSIS OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the successful information from each of the modern methods of teaching a foreign language, independent educational technologies. It allows students to adjust any technology in accordance with the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of teaching a specific group of students.

Keywords: Independent educational technology, communication method, essay, essay-reflection, discussion, dialogue, pedagogical system.

Language is the most important means of communication, without which the existence and development of human society is impossible. Today, changes in social relations, means of communication (the use of new information technologies) require students to increase their communicative competence, improve their philological preparation, exchange ideas in various situations in the process of interaction with other participants in communication, as well as the correct use of the system of language and speech norms and the choice of communicative behavior adequate to the real communication situation. In other words, the main goal of a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, that is, the ability to conduct interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language with native speakers. The educational aspect is an integral part of the educational process, therefore, all educational technologies ensure the upbringing of the necessary qualities of a mature personality in students.

Modern educational technologies used to form students' communicative competence in a foreign language are considered the most effective for creating an educational environment that ensures the person-oriented interaction of all participants in the educational process. It is clear that the use of any educational technology, no matter how perfect it is, cannot create the most effective conditions for the emergence and development of students' abilities and the teacher's creative search. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with the lack of positive motivation for learning a foreign language in some students. Positive motivation is insufficient, and sometimes absent, because they experience great difficulties in learning a foreign language and do not master the material due to their psychological characteristics. The main goal of the independent learning method is to provide

students with the opportunity to independently acquire knowledge in the process of solving practical issues or problems that require the integration of knowledge from different disciplines. If we talk about this method as a pedagogical technology, then this technology implies a complex of research, investigation, problem-solving methods of a creative nature. Inside, the role of a project developer, coordinator, expert, consultant is determined for the teacher.

This technology develops students' creativity, develops their imagination and interests. In the process of preparing independent tasks, the creative and intellectual potential of students is revealed. The project method teaches to conduct research, work in a team, conduct discussions, solve problems. Life in modern society requires students to develop such important cognitive abilities as developing their own thinking, understanding experience, building a chain of evidence, and expressing their thoughts clearly and convincingly.

The technology for developing independent thinking involves asking students questions and understanding the problem to be solved. Critical thinking is of an individual independent nature, everyone creates their own ideas, forms their own assessments and beliefs independently of others, finds a solution to the problem themselves and confirms it with rational, well-founded and reliable evidence.

Independent thinking is social, since each idea is tested and shared with others. The active life position of the student is especially manifested when comparing previously existing knowledge and concepts with newly acquired knowledge. There are various forms of work that ensure the development of independent thinking of students: essay, essay-reflection, discussion, dialogue, role-playing, etc. To develop intercultural communication skills, it is important to give students complete knowledge of the culture, customs and traditions of the English-speaking country, so that students have an objective idea and can consciously choose their own communication style.

Modeling situations of intercultural communication in English lessons allows students to compare the features of the lifestyle of people in our country and in the countries of the language being studied, helps them better understand the culture of our country and develops the ability to express it through English. Such an approach is possible only when using authentic teaching aids.

Information and communication technologies are increasingly finding application in the organization of the educational process, allowing to effectively consider all possible aspects (from linguistics to cultural studies), improving the

speech activity of a foreign language. Their use helps to improve the linguistic and intercultural competences of students, to form a culture of communication in an electronic environment, to increase information culture in general, as well as to develop computer skills: search, processing, transmission, systematization. presentation of information and results of research activities by students. The basis of interactive approaches is interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The main difference between independently performed exercises and simple ones is that they are aimed not only at consolidating the studied material, but also at learning new ones.

When it comes to the practical application of technologies, it is not at all necessary to use one technology. The best way was to combine several educational technologies, combining their best aspects. When we are engaged in the integration of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to form independent learning of the student, it is necessary to carefully study the innovative ideas of modern Russian and foreign teachers for several years.

It is concluded that this pedagogical system helps to reveal the subjective experience of students, to form personally significant educational methods for them, to educate moral ideals, to develop critical thinking, to adequately assess and self-manage.

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